

Online Voting System for India Based

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Abstract—

This thesis investigates different existing open-source Web Content Management Systems (WCMS) and their features. The main objective of WCMS is to allow non-technical users to easily update and manage a website's content. But WCMS products available on the market today have integrated many other complex functionalities, which makes the user interface difficult to understand and use. All WCMS require some amount of training on installation and where to start. After integration users need to read the manual or take lessons to use other available advanced features. The research question explored here is whether to implement a WCMS from existing options compared with the feasibility of building a new one from scratch. This paper discusses the considerations of developing a new WCMS, including the advantages and disadvantages relative to an off-the-shelf product.

Keywords— WCMS

1. INTRODUCTION

Content management (CM) is the set of processes and technologies that support the collection, managing, and publishing of information in any form or medium. Content may take the form of text (such as documents), multimedia files (such as audio or video files), or any other file type that follows a content lifecycle requiring management. Content management is an inherently collaborative process. It often consists of the following basic roles and responsibilities:

- Creator: responsible for creating and editing content.
- Editor: responsible for modifying the style of delivery, including translation and localization.
- Publisher: responsible for releasing the content for use.
- Administrator: responsible for managing access permissions to folders and files, usually accomplished by assigning access rights to user groups or roles.
- Consumer, viewer, or guest: the person who reads or otherwise takes in content after it is published or shared [1].

1.1 WHAT IS A CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (CMS)?

A content management system (CMS) is a computer system or an application that allows publishing, editing, or modification of content, as well as site maintenance, from a central page [2]. The content on the World Wide Web consists of HTML, XML, and other documents and media files. This content can be published manually by editing and organizing files on a file system exposed to the web through a web server, requiring much technical expertise and tedious work. Content management systems store the actual content which can be text or images in a database. The system then automatically pulls the content out and shows it on appropriate pages based on the rules. Content management systems were created to help people publish

documents and media with less technical intervention and in a more consistent and automated fashion. Anything from a document management system, to a media asset management system, to a portal, to a blog system could be considered a Content Management System [3].

Content management system speeds up the content updating process and makes it easy for a non-technical user. This helps in keeping the content up-to-date and timely. They are frequently used for editing, controlling, versioning and publishing specific documentation. They are used for different types of applications to manage its content.

Below are some of the CMS applications.

- Blogs: comments on a particular topic;
- News: reading newspapers online instead of reading the hard/physical copy;
- Wikis: these are open to public editing.

The core features of Content Management Systems vary widely from system to system; many simpler systems provide only a handful of features, while others, especially enterprise systems, are much more complex and powerful.

- Allow for a large number of people to share and contribute to stored data;
- Control access to data based on user role (i.e., define information users or user groups can view, edit, publish, etc.);
- Facilitate storage and retrieval of data;
- Control data validity;
- Simplify report writing;
- Define data as almost anything: documents, movies, texts, pictures, phone numbers, articles etc. [2].

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lifecycle requiring management. Content management is an inherently collaborative process.

1.2 PROJECT DEFINITION AND PURPOSE

In this thesis, I have built a Simple CMS which is a web content management system that can be used to dynamically manage the content of a simple static HTML website. For eg. the news section of the Computer Science Department needs to be updated very often and since it is static HTML page, a technical person having knowledge of HTML and CSS is required to update even a small portion of the section. The primary objective of this thesis is to demonstrate how Simple CMS engine could be integrated with the "News & Events" section page of the San Diego State University's Computer Science department, so that the process of updating the content becomes faster and easier for the department. The main purpose of this project is to have a user-friendly content administration interface that includes most common CMS functions appropriate for small and simple websites, so that a novice user can manage the website content. A user having less coding knowledge can easily add, edit and format the website's content using the rich text editor integrated in the Simple CMS engine without having to deal with the HTML and CSS code.

1.3 CONTENT OVERVIEW

The remainder of the thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 2 describes different types of CMS, compares the most popular open source CMS and discusses their advantages and disadvantages. It also discusses the advantages and limitations of this project. Chapter 3 describes different tools and technologies used to build this project- Simple CMS. Chapter 4 describes the common CMS features implemented in this project. In addition to that, it also describes the high level architecture, database architecture and implementation of Simple CMS. Finally Chapter 5, a conclusion and

description of future work in this project to help contribute more for websites requiring more advanced functions in addition to the common basic CMS features available in the project.

2. TOOLS

Several technological tools were used in this project; each is summarized in the sections that follow.

2.1 HTML

HTML stands for Hyper Text Markup Language. A markup language is a language that annotates text in a way that is syntactically distinguishable so that the computer can manipulate it. It is a set of markup tags used to describe web pages. The tags are what separate normal text from HTML code. They are the words between the <angle-brackets>. Different tags will perform different functions, like rendering images or tables. It is a combination of words and symbols which give instructions on how the document will be presented. The tags themselves don't appear when you view your page through a browser, but their effects do. Markup is what HTML tags do to the text inside them. They mark it as a certain type of text (italicized text, for example) [20]. HTML documents contain HTML tags and plain text. The content on a HTML page will be static. In order to change the content, the editor needs to have some knowledge about HTML and change the content accordingly.

2.2 CSS

CSS stands for Cascading Style Sheets. It is used to control the style and layout of multiple web pages all at once. Styles define how to display HTML elements. CSS overrides the browser's default settings for interpreting how tags should be displayed, letting you use any HTML element indicated by an opening and closing tag to apply style attributes defined either locally or in a style sheet.

External Style Sheets can save a lot of work. They are stored in CSS files.

Style sheets contain rules, composed of

selectors and declarations that define how styles will be applied. The selector (a redefined HTML element, class name, or ID name) is the link between the HTML document and the style. There are two different kinds of selectors: types (HTML element tags) and attributes (such as class and ID names) [21].

2.3 JAVASCRIPT

JavaScript is a client side scripting language designed to add interactivity to HTML pages. A scripting language is a lightweight programming language. It is usually embedded directly into HTML pages. It is an interpreted language which allows the scripts to execute without preliminary compilation.

JavaScript can react to events. A JavaScript can be set to execute when something happens, like when a page has finished loading or when a user clicks on an HTML element. JavaScript can read and write HTML elements and can also change it's content and properties. A JavaScript can be used to validate form data before it is submitted to a server. This saves the server from extra processing. A JavaScript can be used to detect the visitor's browser, and depending on the browser, load another page specifically designed for that browser. Finally, JavaScript can be used to create cookies and to store and retrieve information on the visitor's computer [22].

2.4 PHP

PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) is a widely-used open source server-side scripting language for web development and can be embedded into HTML. PHP pages contain HTML with embedded code [23]. PHP offers several advantages:

PHP runs on different platforms (Windows, Linux, Unix, etc.). PHP is compatible with almost all servers used today (Apache, IIS, etc.). PHP is free to download from the official PHP resource: www.php.net. PHP is easy to learn and runs efficiently on the server side [24]. What distinguishes PHP from something like client-side JavaScript is that the code is

executed on the server, generating HTML, which is then sent to the client. The client receives the results of running that script, but does not know what the underlying code was [23].

2.5 MYSQL

MySQL is a database server is ideal for both small and large applications. It supports standard SQL and compiles on a number of platforms. It is free to download and use [24].

3.6 JQUERY

jQuery is a fast and concise JavaScript Library that simplifies HTML document Traversing, event handling, animating, and Ajax interactions for rapid web development. jQuery is designed to change the way JavaScript is written. Therefore jQuery greatly simplifies JavaScript programming [25]. This project specifically uses jQuery for form validation and to implement tabbed menu.

It is free, open source software. Dual-licensed under the MIT License or the GNU General Public License, jQuery's syntax is designed to make it easier to navigate a document, select DOM elements, create animations, handle events, and develop Ajax applications. jQuery also provides capabilities for developers to create plug-ins on top of the JavaScript library. This enables developers to create abstractions for low-level interaction and animation, advanced effects and high-level, theme-able widgets. The modular approach to the jQuery library allows the creation of powerful dynamic web pages and web applications.

jQuery includes the following features:

- DOM traversal and modification
- DOM manipulation based on CSS selectors that uses node elements name and node elements attributes (id and class) as criteria to build selectors
- Events
- Effects and animations
- Ajax
- Extensibility through plug-ins
- Utilities - such as user agent

information, feature detection

- Compatibility methods that are natively available in modern browsers but need fallbacks for older ones (for example, the `inArray()` and `each()` functions) ? Cross-browser support [26].

3 FEATURES, DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter discusses the various features, architecture and design components of the project. Screen images of the graphical user interface for select functions are in the Appendix.

3.1 SYSTEM OVERVIEW

Web based voting framework has a few critical advances. The framework is congenial from two sides: (I) From the Election Commission of India side who is likewise the Administrator. (ii) From the voter side.

Essential strides of web based voting framework are portrayed in following areas.

A. Uploading voter Information

In the web based voting framework, all the data of every voter is included/transferred in fundamental database of Election Commission of India as indicated by AADHAAR Identity Number. This AADHAAR Identity number is extraordinary for each resident or voter of India. This AADHAAR Identity number has been presented by administration of India and this likewise perceives the voting public of the voter. Be that as it may, the enlistment of the voter ought to be finished simply after the confirmation of all archives by the field officer. The field officer likewise checks AADHAAR Identity Number from the principle AADHAAR card database. Subsequent to finishing check, the enrollment of the voter ought to be finished and the voter will get auto produced email which has all these data of the voter with the framework created secret key. The Voter can utilize this secret word for login and he/she can likewise change the framework produced old watchword. Voter can likewise set the confirmation keys to guarantee security. There ought to be limitation to utilize just virtual/on

screen console to type watchword or to change secret key. Primary reason for utilizing virtual/on screen console is to quit catching secret word, if voter changes his/her watchword from some open place.

B. Uploading candidate Information

In internet voting framework, the competitor sends all his/her in arrangement with AADHAAR Identity number to the Administrator and simply in the wake of confirming the hopeful data, the Administrator will enlist candidate as per his/her voting public. At this stage the Administrator likewise gives a one of a kind applicant ID to every contender to make a hopeful novel. Candidate profile image and Party symbol are also added in this phase with to her information. AADHAAR Identity number is compulsory for every candidate to register.

Input/ Output scenario of online voting system

Figure 1. A sample e-ballot paper.

C. Date and time of Election

In this phase, the Administrator finalizes and sets the date of election along with starting and ending timings of the election. Administrator sets time zone according to India which is +5.30 offset from GMT. The voters who are outside of their constituency area can also vote according to in date time zone on Election Day.

D. Election Day

On the day of election, the Election

Commission of India arranges the mobile booths in all the voting constituent area. Then the Administrator opens the voting website server till the closing time and all the registered voter can vote easily/directly from their preferred location.

E. Vote Submission

In this phase, the voter first login their respective election account with his/her unique AADHAAR id and password. In the account, the voter verifies all his/ her details and after completing verification, voter moves to the e-ballot paper. The e-ballot paper contains all the information of the candidate such as candidate name, candidate AADHAAR id, candidate party logo, candidate background detail option button, party name, candidate profile picture, button for seeing other party member with their background. Fig.1 shows a sample of e-ballot paper.

Voter selects button of the favorite candidate and finally press "SUBMIT VOTE" button. After pressing ng "SUBMIT VOTE" button the security checking will be done automatic ally by the server.

E -ballot paper

ADHAAR ID	CANDIDATE NAME	IMAGE	CANDIDATE PROFILE	PARTY SYMBOL	PARTY NAME	SUBMIT VOTE
234323435076	HAGARWAL		☐		BJP	
654567652256	YNATA		☐		CONGRESS	
897378996756	L.KUMAR		☐		BSP	
987644569009	N.JAIN		☐		SP	
243568875551	K.PRATAP		☐		RJD	
864345789876	N.ROY		☐		NRD	
986367875795	R.SHETTY		☐		NRD	

F. Acceptance of vote by server

The security check of the voter is done automatic ally by the server. In this phase when the voter submits his/her vote by pressing the

button "SUBMIT VOTE", then the server will immediately ask the high security submission password. The voter receive s this high security password on his/her personal mobile at same time. Only after entering correct high security submission password given, the server will ask for the finger prints for authentication and when the finger prints will be matched with the database of the server, the vote will be accepted by the Election Commission of India and District Magistrate else the server will ask one more time for the finger prints and will match with the server database if this time also it doesn't match then the user will be blocked to vote. All the votes given by voters stored in main database of Election Commission of India and District magistrate election office. Fig.2 shows the security checking process during vote submission.

Diagram for security checking

REFERENCES

1. Tadayoshi Kohno, Adam Stubblefield, Aviel D. Rubin, Dan S. Wallach, "Analysis of an Electronic Voting System", Johns Hopkins University Information Security Institute Technical Report, TR-2003-19, July 23, 2003
2. http://newindianexpress.com/states/andhra_pradesh/Maoists-strike-fear-make-off-with-poll-papers-in-agency/2013/07/15/article1684243. ece
3. Executive Summary of "Genesis and Spread of Maoist Violence and Appropriate State Strategy to Handle it", Bureau of Police Research and Development, Ministry of Home Affairs, New Delhi
4. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electronic_voting
5. David L. Dill, Bruce Schneier, and Barbara Simons, "Voting and technology: Who gets to count your vote?", Communications of the ACM, vol. 46(8), Aug. 2003, pp. 29–31
6. David Jefferson, Aviel D. Rubin, Barbara Simons, and David Wagner, "Analyzing Internet voting security", Communications of the ACM, vol. 47(10), Oct. 2004, pp. 59–64
7. David Evans and Nathanael Paul, "Election security: Perception and reality", IEEE Security & Privacy, vol. 2(1), Jan. 2004, pp. 24–31
8. Rebecca Mercuri. "Statement on electronic voting" <http://www.notablessoftware.com/RMstatement.html>, 2007
9. Title:- "Enhanced Data Security in Network Environment" Page No.- 396-405, Vol.- 14 ISSUE- 04 Month – April Year- 2016
10. Title:- "A Study of web portal features as a knowledge management in school education" Page No.- 1-4, Vol.-05 ISSUE- 5 Month – Feb Year- 2016
11. Title:- "A Study of Security Mechanisms Implemented in Network Protocols" Page No.- 1-3, Vol.- 05 ISSUE- 11 Month – December Year- 2015
12. Title:- "Network Security Mechanisms Through OSI/ISO Network Model for Upper Layers" Page No.- 1-4, Vol.- 05 ISSUE- 6 Month – December Year- 2015
13. Title:- "Developing and analyzing portal Based Knowledge management solution" Page No.- 0143-0147, Vol.- 02 ISSUE- 8 Month – October Year- 2014
14. Title:- "Nutritional importance and health benefits of Mushroom for women and Overview" Page No.- 0143-0147, Vol.- 03 ISSUE- 1 Month – March Year- 2013
15. Title:- "A Impact of ICT enabled Distance Learning models on learners performance" Page No.- 79-86, Vol.- 05 ISSUE- 02 Month – July-December Year- 2012
16. Title:- "Impact of Web Enabled knowledge platform: An Analysis" Page No.- 1-7, Vol.- 04 ISSUE- 1 Month – June Year- 2012
17. Title:- "APQN Beyond first decade of 21 century" Page No.- 16-19, Vol.- 15 ISSUE- 04 Month – January Year- 2012
18. Title:- "Measuring effectiveness of ICT tools teaching school children: A Case study from Chhattisgarh state , India" Page No.- 29-34, Vol.- 06 ISSUE- 3 Month – December Year- 2010
19. Title:- "Laptop Distribution Among Engineering graduate students in Chhattisgarh: A Brief Perspective" Page No.- 050-054, Vol.- 01 ISSUE- 31 Month – July Year- 2017
20. Title:- "Analyzing Laptop Distribution and Effects Among Engineering students in Chhattisgarh:" Page No.- 027-035, Vol.- 02 ISSUE- 19 Month – June Year- 2017
21. Title:- "A Study of network Attacks and Features of Secure Protocols" Page No.- 1-3, Vol.- 08 ISSUE- 1 Month – March Year- 2017

Other References:

